

The Influence of Situational Leadership, Work Environment, Competence, and Motivation on Employee Job Satisfaction at the National Library of Indonesia

Prisla Yanuardi Tulus Putra¹, Setyo Riyanto²

¹Master of Management student Universitas Mercu Buana, Jakarta Indonesia

²Associate Professor Universitas Mercu Buana, Jakarta Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to determine the effect of situational leadership, work environment, competence, and motivation on employee satisfaction at the National Library. The research population is the National Library employees who work in the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services, with a total sample of 195 people. The design of this research is quantitative research with a data analysis method using multiple linear regression. The results of the study state that situational leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction, the work environment has a positive and significant impact on employee job satisfaction, competence has a positive and significant impact on employee job satisfaction, and motivation has a positive and significant impact on employee job satisfaction. Situational leadership, work environment, competence and motivation together have a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Competence, Job Satisfaction, Motivation, Situational Leadership, Work Environment

INTRODUCTION

The development of science and information technology accompanied by changes in social life aspects requires creating people who like to read. Can use interest in reading to show whether a nation is progressing or not. Intelligence and knowledge are benchmarks for the civilization of a country. The breadth of knowledge will produce intelligence and knowledge. At the same time, the amount of information will become a science. The more comprehensive the knowledge of a nation's population, the broader its civilization. Interest in reading in Indonesia is far behind when compared to other countries in the world. According to UNESCO data in 2012, Indonesia's reading interest is only 0.001 per cent. That is, there are 1 in 1,000 people who have a severe interest in reading. Indonesia ranks 60th out of 61 countries regarding reading interest based on the 2016 Most Literate Nation In The World survey. One of the factors that cause low reading interest is the availability of reading materials.

Comparison of the availability of reading materials with the number of residents is far different One of the limitations of this reading material can be seen from the number of libraries. In November 2018, the National Library recorded the number of libraries throughout Indonesia, reaching 164,610 libraries. Of these, 19.48% or 30,838 libraries are considered to meet national standards. Meanwhile, 0.58% or 910 libraries are accredited with National Library Standards (SNP). There are 42,460 public libraries, 6,552 university libraries, 2,057 special libraries, and 113,541 school libraries out of the entire libraries throughout Indonesia. With the distribution of libraries 47.79% in Java, 23.45% in Sumatra, 11.52% in Sulawesi, 8.47% in Nusa Tenggara, 6.67% in Kalimantan, and 0.4% in Papua. Meanwhile, the availability of reading materials owned by libraries throughout Indonesia totals 16,077,296 pieces.

As a Non-Ministerial Government Institution (LPNK), the National Library continues to innovate services and build all types of libraries as facilities for access to information and knowledge to increase public interest in reading. The National Library seeks to facilitate and encourage increased interest in reading by providing quality reading materials and providing library facilities and infrastructure that are easily accessible. The National Library is required to provide excellent service to the community to increase interest in reading and broaden insight and knowledge to educate the nation's life. Can realize this if the National Library can fulfil employee job satisfaction because employees are the most important asset owned by the National Library. Employees have an essential role in the progress of the National Library. Employee job satisfaction affects the employee's performance. Employees will give a good performance if the employee is satisfied and happy to work at the National Library. If employees are

comfortable and happy to work at the National Library, of course, employees will provide high loyalty and try to improve their abilities and skills in achieving the stated goals, namely increasing interest in reading in Indonesia.

Regarding job satisfaction of employees at the National Library, the authors conducted a pre-survey by distributing brief questionnaires, which consisted of indicators regarding job satisfaction to 32 employees. The pre-survey result stated that the overall job satisfaction of the National Library employees was not as expected, and we could see from the results of the pre-survey that employees at the National Library felt that the income provided by the agency had not been able to provide employee job satisfaction. Some employees who are dissatisfied with the work being done, then employees feel less attention to the circumstances and conditions of the employee, and there are still employees who feel unhappy with their co-workers because they cannot be invited to work together.

Leaders at work play a vital role in ensuring the overall functioning of the organization they lead. Situational leadership can affect employee job satisfaction. The existence of good work synergy between leaders and employees will be able to increase employee job satisfaction. A research gap on the influence of situational leadership on job satisfaction is the basis for the author to examine the effect of situational leadership on employee job satisfaction in the National Library. This can be seen from previous research conducted by Mattalatta (2019), which stated that situational leadership had a significant effect on employee job satisfaction. In a study conducted by Hardono (2020), situational leadership had no partial impact on job satisfaction.

The work environment is also one of the factors that can affect employee job satisfaction to achieve company goals. A research gap on the influence of the work environment on job satisfaction is the basis for the author to examine the effect of the work environment on employee job satisfaction in the National Library. Can be seen from the results of research conducted by Yunsepa (2018), which states that the work environment has a positive and significant influence on satisfaction and the results of a study conducted by Apriyani (2020) work environment has a negative and insignificant effect.

Employee competence can also affect employee job satisfaction. Competent employees with skills, attitudes and high appreciation will undoubtedly help the company achieve the goals set in the future, and vice versa with these employees will have their pride for their performance and get job satisfaction. A research gap on employee competence with job satisfaction is the basis for the author to examine employee job satisfaction at the National Library. Can be seen from the results of research conducted by Riyadi (2017), which states that competence has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, and a study conducted by Yunsepa (2018) says that competence has no significant impact on job satisfaction.

Motivation is an encouragement to employees to carry out their work to foster morale in achieving organizational goals. A research gap on the influence of motivation on job satisfaction is the basis for researchers to examine the effect of motivation on employee job satisfaction in the National Library. Can be seen from the results of research conducted by Riyadi (2017), which states that motivation has a positive and significant influence on job satisfaction and the consequences of a study conducted by Rahayu (2020) where motivation does not affect job satisfaction.

From the description above, employees job satisfaction at the National Library has not been as expected. So this raises questions for researchers to measure employee job satisfaction at the National Library, which needs to be reviewed to maximize that employee job satisfaction. Thus the purpose of this study is to determine whether situational leadership has an effect on employee job satisfaction at the National Library, to determine whether the work environment affects employee job satisfaction at the National Library, to determine whether competence has an effect on employee job satisfaction at the National Library, to determine whether motivation affects employee job satisfaction at the National Library, to find out whether situational leadership, work environment, competence, and motivation simultaneously affect employee job satisfaction at the National Library. The research limitation in this study was carried out at the research location, namely the Deputy for Library Material Development and National Library Information Services.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Situational Leadership

According to Schermehorn (2012), leadership situational focuses on the maturity level and readiness of followers. Robbins (2012) says that situational leadership is leadership that focuses on the willingness of followers. The factors that influence situational leadership are the first to understand the character of the subordinates and the second to look at the ongoing situation before

determining the leadership pattern to be taken. Based on the theory of the experts above, we can define in general that situational leadership is the behaviour of leaders who adapt to different situations and conditions of subordinates.

Situational leadership indicators used in this study are situational leadership models according to Paul Hersey and Kent Blanchard in Haryono (2015), namely:

1. S1 Style: Telling Style
2. S2 Style: Selling/Coaching Style
3. S3 Style: Participatory / Supportive Style
4. S4 Style: Delegative Style

B. Work Environment

According to Sedarmayanti (2011), the work environment is the entire tooling and material faced, the surrounding environment in which a person works, his work methods, and work arrangements both as individuals and as groups. According to Sutrisno (2019), the work environment is the overall work facilities and infrastructure around employees who are doing work that can affect the implementation of the work. This work environment includes the workplace, facilities and works aids, cleanliness, lighting, tranquillity, including the working relationship between the people in the place.

According to Nitisemito in Naa (2017), the work environment consists of several indicators, namely:

1. Work atmosphere
2. Availability of facilities for employees
3. Relationships with colleagues

C. Competence

Competence comes from the word competence which means skill, ability, and authority (Scale in Sutrisno, 2019). According to Armstrong and Baron in Wibowo (2017), competence is a behavioural dimension behind competent performance. Competence is an ability to carry out or perform a job or task based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitude required by the job (Wibowo, 2017).

As for the indicators of competence according to Hutapea and Nurianna in Yuningsih (2019), namely:

1. Knowledge related to work
2. Individual skills
3. Work attitude

D. Motivation

Motivation is something that creates enthusiasm or work motivation (Sutrisno, 2019). Fillmore H. Stanford in Mangkunegara (2017) defines motivation as a condition that moves people towards a specific goal. Hasibuan (2019) states that work motivation is the provision of a driving force that creates one's work enthusiasm so that they want to work together, work effectively, and be integrated with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction. Motivation can be defined as a driving force from within and within the subject to carry out certain activities to achieve specific goals (Riyanto, 2017).

According to Herzberg quoted in Aima (2017), motivation is divided into two factors, namely motivators or commonly called intrinsic motivation and hygiene factors or commonly called extrinsic incentives motivations which are separated into two dimensions, where each size affects one particular aspect of job satisfaction. Hygiene factors prevent job dissatisfaction but do not affect job satisfaction.

According to David McClelland in Mangkunegara (2017), three kinds of human needs are used as indicators of motivation: achievement motivation, motivation to power, motivation to an affiliate.

E. Job Satisfaction

According to Sutrisno (2019), job satisfaction is the attitude of employees towards their work related to work situations, cooperation between employees, rewards received at work, and matters relating to physical and psychological factors. Luthans in Aksan (2017) says that job satisfaction is a positive emotional state of a person arising from an appreciation for a job he has done. Robbins in Aksan (2017) defines job satisfaction as a general attitude towards a person's work, the difference between the amount of reward a worker receives and the amount they believe they should receive.

five dimensions affect job satisfaction that can be used as indicators of job satisfaction as revealed by Luthans in Aksan (2017), namely:

1. The work itself
2. Salary
3. Promotion opportunity
4. Supervision
5. Coworkers

F. Conceptual Framework and Hypothesis

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The hypothesis in this study, as follows:

- H1: Situational leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the National Library
- H2: The work environment has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the National Library
- H3: Competence has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the National Library
- H4: Motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the National Library
- H5: Situational leadership, work environment, competence, and motivation together have a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction at the National Library

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is associative research with a quantitative approach. The survey method is the type of research used in this study.

In this study, the population in this study were all employees of the National Library who worked in the work unit of the Deputy for Development of Library Materials and Information Services, which were approximately 381 people.

The sample used in this study were 195 people with an error rate of 5%. The sampling technique used in this study is the Probability Sampling technique, and the sampling technique used is Simple Random Sampling.

A Questionnaire is a data collection technique carried out in this study using a Likert scale as a measurement scale.

This study uses multiple linear regression analysis contained in the SPSS (Statistics Program for Special Science) software to examine the effect of several variables (X), namely situational leadership, work environment, competence and motivation on the dependent variable (Y), namely job satisfaction.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics of respondents in this study can be seen that of the 195 respondents, the majority of 113 respondents or 58% are female. While the rest, as many as 82 employees or 42%, are men. By age category, the most 91 employees (47%) are employees aged 21 to 30 years old, followed by respondents aged 31 to 40 years as many as 76 employees (39%), ages 41 to 50 years old as many as 21 employees (11%), and age 51 years and over as many as 7 employees (4%). And from the education category, the most

151 employees (78%) are employees with an education level of S1/D4. Then followed by respondents with a postgraduate education level of 36 employees (18%) and an education level of D1/D2/D3 as many as 8 employees (4%).

B. Validity and Reliability Test

Table 1. Validity and Reliability Test

Variable	Number of Statements	Range of Value (r-count)	r-table	Cronbach Alpha	Desc
Situational Leadership (X1)	10	0,384 - 0,840	0,140	0,887	Valid and Reliable
Work Environment (X2)	9	0,270 - 0,711	0,140	0,737	Valid and Reliable
Competence (X3)	7	0,621 - 0,768	0,140	0,832	Valid and Reliable
Motivation (X4)	6	0,525 - 0,733	0,140	0,676	Valid and Reliable
Job Satisfaction (Y)	10	0,378 - 0,705	0,140	0,735	Valid and Reliable

Sources: Primary Data Processed (2021)

All variables are declared valid because $r\text{-count} > r\text{-table}$ and all variables are reliable because $\text{Cronbach alpha} > 0.60$.

C. Normality test

Figure 2. Normality test

From the standard probability plot in the figure above, can see that the data points form a linear pattern so that it can be considered consistent with the normal distribution.

D. Multicollinearity Test

Table 2. Multicollinearity Test

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)		
Situational Leadership	.640	1.562
Work Environment	.656	1.524
Competence	.798	1.253
Motivation	.799	1.251

Source: Primary Data Processed (2021)

The results obtained that the value of all VIF values < 10 means that there is no multicollinearity, and it is concluded that it meets the multicollinearity test.

E. Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 3. Heteroscedasticity Test

From the picture above, it can be seen that there is no heteroscedasticity because there is no clear pattern and the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y-axis. So can say that the heteroscedasticity test is fulfilled.

F. Coefficient of Determination (Adjusted R Square)

Table 3. Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.632 ^a	.399	.386	.21769

Source: Primary Data Processed (2021)

Adjusted R square of 0.386 or 38.6%, indicating that job satisfaction is influenced by the four independent variables used in this study (i.e. independent situational leadership (X1), work environment (X2), competence (X3) and motivation (X4)) 38.6%. There is still influence from other factors, namely 61.4% from other factors.

G. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.086	0.294		3.699	0.000
	Situational Leadership	0.099	0.043	0.163	2.317	0.022
	Work Environment	0.273	0.057	0.333	4.799	0.000
	Competence	0.212	0.068	0.196	3.114	0.002
	Motivation	0.144	0.044	0.207	3.296	0.001

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction.

Sources: Primary Data Processed (2021)

The results of the multiple linear regression test in the study:

$$Y = 1.086 + 0.099X1 + 0.273X2 + 0.212X3 + 0.144X4$$

From the regression equation formed above, the interpretation can be explained as follows:

- a. β_0 (constant) = 1.086, meaning that the value of the job satisfaction variable (Y) is 1.086 if the variables of situational leadership (X1), work environment (X2), competence (X3), and motivation (X4) do not exist or are equal to zero.
- b. $\beta_1 = 0.099$, meaning that if the situational leadership variable (X1) increases and other variables remain constant, the job satisfaction variable (Y) will increase by 0.099.
- c. $\beta_2 = 0.273$, meaning that if the work environment variable (X2) increases and other variables remain constant, the job satisfaction variable (Y) will increase by 0.273.
- d. $\beta_3 = 0.212$, meaning that if the competency variable (X3) increases and other variables remain constant, the job satisfaction variable (Y) will increase by 0.212.
- e. $\beta_4 = 0.144$, meaning that if the motivation variable (X4) increases and other variables remain constant, the job satisfaction variable (Y) will increase by 0.144.

1. T-Test

a. Situational Leadership Variables

The situational leadership variable shows a significance value of 0.022. Because the value is below 0.05, it can be said to be significant. The test using the t test is, the value of the t table at alpha 0.05 (one tail) $df = n-1 = 195-1 = 194$ is 1.652. while the calculated t value in the table above is $t\text{-test} = 2,317$. It means that $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$, thus showing that situational leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

Situational leadership has a positive and significant influence on the job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services. This is in line with research conducted by Mattalata (2019), which states that situational leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction and is further strengthened by a study conducted by Farhaeni (2020), which says that situational leadership has a positive and significant impact on job satisfaction. This means that changes in the value of situational leadership have a unidirectional effect on changes in employee job satisfaction or other words, if situational leadership increases, there will be an increase in the level of job satisfaction of employees at the National Library. They work in the work unit of the Deputy for Development of Library Materials and Information Services.

b. Work Environment Variables

The work environment variable shows a Significance value of 0.000. Because the value is below 0.05, it can be said to be significant. The test using the t test is, the value of the t table at alpha 0.05 (one tail) $df = n-1 = 195-1 = 194$ is 1.652. while the t value in the table above is $t\text{-test} = 4.799$. $T\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ shows that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

The work environment has a positive and significant influence on the job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services. This is in line with research conducted by Kusumadewi (2018), which states that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction and is further strengthened by the results of research conducted by Rahayu (2020), which states that the work environment affects job satisfaction. it means that changes in the value of the work environment have a direct effect on changes in employee job satisfaction or other words if the work environment is appropriate, there will be an increase in the level of job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services.

c. Competence Variables

The competence variable shows a significance value of 0.002. Because the value is below 0.05, it can be said to be significant. The test using the t test is, the value of the t table at alpha 0.05 (one tail) $df = n-1 = 195-1 = 194$ is 1.652. while the t value in the table above is $t\text{-test} = 3.114$. $T\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ thus shows that competence has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

Competence has a positive and significant influence on the job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services. This is in line with research conducted by Sunya (2017), which says that competence has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction and is further strengthened by the

results of a study conducted by Kaban (2020), which says that competence has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. This means that changes in the value of competence have a direct impact on changes in employee job satisfaction or other words, if competence increases, there will be an increase in the level of job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services.

d. Motivation Variable

The motivation variable shows a Significance value of 0.001. Because the value is below 0.05, it can be said to be significant. The test using the t test is, the value of the t table at alpha 0.05 (one tail) $df = n-1 = 195-1 = 194$ is 1.652. while the t value in the table above is $t\text{-test} = 3.296$. $T\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ thus shows that motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Motivation has a positive and significant influence on the job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services. This is in line with research conducted by Runi (2017), which states that motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction and is strengthened by Adam (2019), which also says that motivation has a positive and significant impact on job satisfaction. This means that changes in the value of motivation have a direct effect on changes in employee job satisfaction or other words, if motivation increases, there will be an increase in the level of job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services.

2. F-Test

The F test was conducted to determine the effect of situational leadership, work environment, competence and motivation on job satisfaction simultaneously. The value of Sig. of 0.000 indicates that the alpha significance level of 0.05 (one-tailed) is significant. As for testing with the F-test is to compare the value of the F-table with F-count. The value of F-count is 31,536, F-table is 2,420 (see table F), thus the result of F count ($31,536 > 2,420$). Can conclude that situational leadership, work environment, competence, motivation together have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services.

Situational leadership, work environment, competence, motivation together (simultaneously) have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services. This is reinforced by Putra (2017), which states that situational leadership and motivation have a positive effect on job satisfaction. Deswarta (2017), from the results of his research, says that competence and motivation significantly affect on job satisfaction. And a study conducted by Suprapti (2020) says that the work environment and motivation significantly affect job satisfaction. This means that changes in the value of situational leadership, work environment, competence, motivation together have a unidirectional effect on changes in job satisfaction or other words, if situational leadership, work environment, competence, and motivation jointly increase, there will be an increase in the level of job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services.

H. Inter-Dimensional Correlation Matrix

Table 5. Result of Dimensional Correlation Analysis

Variabel	DX	DY				
		Y1.1	Y1.2	Y1.3	Y1.4	Y1.5
Situational Leadership (X1)	X1.1	0.195	0.131	0.269	0.528	0.126
	X1.2	0.044	0.042	0.089	0.019	0.142
	X1.3	0.180	0.113	0.071	0.032	0.098
	X1.4	0.016	0.051	0.018	0.012	0.017
Work Environment (X2)	X2.1	0.190	0.298	0.317	0.244	0.266
	X2.2	0.215	0.366	0.396	0.355	0.291
	X2.3	0.233	0.063	0.015	0.371	0.167
Competence (X3)	X3.1	0.478	0.069	0.201	0.309	0.180
	X3.2	0.515	0.055	0.173	0.324	0.264
	X3.3	0.228	0.116	0.093	0.302	0.023
Motivation (X4)	X4.1	0.330	0.229	0.069	0.270	0.049
	X4.2	0.142	0.194	0.123	0.386	0.008
	X4.3	0.172	0.242	0.208	0.157	0.289

Source: Primary Data Processed (2021)

The table above shows that:

1. For the situational leadership variable, the most vital relationship dimension is the telling style dimension to the supervision dimension on the job satisfaction variable because it has a coefficient value = 0.548 (has a "medium" relationship). While the dimension that is weakly related is the dimension of the delegative style to the dimension of supervision (supervision) on job satisfaction with a value of = 0.012 (has a "very low" relationship).
2. For the work environment variable, the dimension of the strongest relationship is the dimension of work facilities to the promotion dimension on the job satisfaction variable because it has a coefficient value = 0.396 (has a "low" relationship). Meanwhile, the dimension with the weakest relationship is the dimension of the employment relationship to the promotion dimension with a coefficient value of = 0.015 (has a "very low" relationship).
3. For the competency variable, the dimension with the strongest relationship is the skill dimension to the job dimension itself on the job satisfaction variable. It has a coefficient value = 0.515 (has a "medium" relationship). While the dimension with the weakest relationship is the dimension of attitude towards the dimensions of coworkers on the job satisfaction variable, with a coefficient value = 0.023 (having a "very low" relationship).
4. For the motivation variable, the dimension that has the strongest relationship is the dimension of motivation in power to the dimension of supervision (supervision) on the job satisfaction variable because it has a coefficient value = 0.386 (has a "low" relationship). Meanwhile, the dimension with the weakest relationship is the dimension of motivation to power on the dimensions of coworkers on the job satisfaction variable with a coefficient value of = 0.008 (having a "very low" relationship).

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusion

1. Situational leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, meaning that changes in the value of situational leadership have a significant influence on changes in employee job satisfaction or other words, if situational leadership increases, there will be a significant increase in the level of job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services.
2. The work environment has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, meaning that changes in the value of the work environment have a direct impact on changes in employee job satisfaction or other words, if the work environment increases, there will be an increase in the level of job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of Deputy Field of Library Material Development and Information Services.
3. Competency has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, meaning that changes in competency values have a unidirectional impact on changes in employee job satisfaction or other words, if competence increases, there will be an increase in the level of job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Material Development. Library and Information Services.
4. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, meaning that changes in the value of motivation have a direct impact on changes in employee job satisfaction or other words, if motivation increases, there will be an increase in the level of job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Materials Development. Library and Information Services.
5. If tested together, the results are situational leadership, work environment, competence, motivation together (simultaneously) have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Materials and Services Development Information. There is a solid simultaneous relationship between situational leadership, work environment, competence and motivation on job satisfaction for employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services.

B. Suggestions

1. On the situational leadership variable, it can be recommended for every leader in the National Library who works in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services to make SOP (Standard Operating Procedures) and precise work mechanisms. This SOP and work mechanism is used as a reference in carrying out work to accelerate employee job satisfaction. With this SOP and work mechanism, it will be easier for leaders to provide work directions and supervise employees' work. Employees will also better the job done correctly by SOP and existing work mechanisms. Every

leader in the National Library who works in the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services is advised to take leadership education and training to improve leadership abilities, especially situational leadership, to realize employee job satisfaction. In addition, leaders must increase the confidence in employees that employees can carry out their work. With the trust given by the leadership, employees can carry out their work freely without any pressure and intimidation so they can realize that employee job satisfaction.

2. The National Library is advised to improve the physical work environment, specifically related to work facilities within the work unit of the Deputy for Development of Library Materials and Information Services, namely by repairing damaged work facilities, replacing infrastructure that is no longer suitable for use such as computers, desks, chairs, as well as designing a comfortable workspace to work to accelerate the realization of employee job satisfaction at the office located on Jalan Salemba Raya 28A. In addition, it is recommended that the leadership at the National Library who works in the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services work unit improve working relations by creating a discussion forum every month or at least once every three months. This discussion forum can strengthen the working relationship between leaders and employees and employees with other employees. The working relationship will be harmonious and will form a solid work team.
3. The National Library, especially in the Deputy of Development of Library Materials and Information Services, is advised to conduct employee education and training to improve employee skills. With this employee education and training, employee skills will increase, making it easier for employees to work, accelerating employee job satisfaction. In addition, it is recommended that the National Library, especially in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services, can see the attitudes and abilities of subordinates. When subordinates cannot do the job and are not willing, then the leader must take a directing role, telling them what to do. The leader provides a strict workflow to achieve job success and control subordinates. Suppose subordinates can do a good job, and there is a possibility that they are overconfident, then if the leader dictates what to do, of course, it can demotivate them, or there will be resistance. The leader needs to sell other ways to get them to work, explain and clarify existing decisions. The leader here spends time listening and giving advice, even if required, can help subordinates to acquire the necessary skills by coaching. When aids can do a job but refuse to do it, the leader need not worry about showing what to do. The leader must find out why the person is resisting and persuade them to cooperate. The leader here spends time actively listening, praising and otherwise making subordinates feel good when demonstrating the necessary commitment. When aids can do the work and are motivated to do it, the leader can leave them. Leaders can trust them to carry on with the job even if they need supervision to ensure that everything goes as planned.
4. National Library leaders who work in the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services are advised to provide rewards and sanctions (reward and punishment) to accelerate the realization of employee satisfaction. With rewards and punishments, it encourages high work motivation in employees, where this motivation is needed to increase employee job satisfaction to achieve the expected performance. In addition, it is also recommended that the Head of the National Library who works in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services, enforce the rules and treat employees fairly without any employees feeling neglected. Because that way, employees will be motivated to work even better.
5. Situational leadership, work environment, competence, motivation together (simultaneously) have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of employees at the National Library who work in the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services. This study further strengthens the theory and concept of a relationship of influence given by situational leadership, work environment, competence, motivation to job satisfaction. This research has limitations, among others, the place of research is still within the scope of the work unit of the Deputy for Development of Library Materials and Information Services and only 4 (four) independent variables, namely situational leadership, work environment, competence, motivation. So it is recommended to conduct further research by looking at the limitations of this research which can be used as a source of ideas for the development of this research in the future, namely expanding the research area which is not only within the scope of the work unit of the Deputy for Library Material Development and Information Services but also all work units at the National Library and added independent variables that affect job satisfaction.

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